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Wittgenstein, Deflationism and Moral Facts

Abstract

This paper discusses the meta-ethical implications of Wittgenstein's later moral philosophy. According to Lovibond and Brandhorst, Wittgenstein provided a novel conception of moral facts, properties and objects by adopting deflationism. Lovibond argues that Wittgenstein's seamless conception of language together with his non-foundational epistemology and non-transcendent understanding of rationality involves a change of perspective towards a plausible and non-mystificatory moral realism. Meanwhile, Brandhorst argues that Wittgenstein's provides a deflationist conception of moral truths from which we can also obtain a deflationist conception of moral facts. This paper argues, on the contrary, that the attribution of deflationism does not do justice to Wittgenstein's later work. It is concluded, therefore, that the appeal to deflationism does not afford or substantiate the exegetical claims made by Lovibond and Brandhorst.

Introduction

During the past decades philosophers have shown a growing interest in understanding Wittgenstein's later moral philosophy and its implications for contemporary meta-ethical debates. Brandhorst and Lovibond have sought to develop a link between Wittgenstein's later philosophy and deflationism in order to shed some light on the meta-ethical implications of his later moral philosophy. Specifically, they suggest that his embrace of deflationism warrants the postulation of moral entities while avoiding the troubles that have traditionally surfaced with regards to moral realism.

This paper critically examines these proposed interpretations by discussing the adequacy of attributing deflationism to Wittgenstein. Section 1 offers an overview of deflationism and some proposals relevant to this paper. Section 2 outlines Lovibond's and Brandhorst's proposed interpretations of Wittgenstein's later moral philosophy. The remainder of the paper discusses the adequacy of invoking Wittgenstein's so-called deflationism to postulate the existence of moral entities.

1. Deflationism

Deflationism is a philosophical program that comes in different shades and stripes. Despite admitting a great deal of variation, deflationists can be understood as sharing the following core negative metaphysical claim: philosophers mistakenly assume that certain properties that are central to philosophy, e.g., truth, reference or existence, are genuine substantive properties that have a nature of the kind one might find out about, investigate and develop theories of by offering informative analysis and reductive generalizations of the form, e.g., x is true *iff* x corresponds to the facts/is made true by truth-makers, x refers to y *iff* x stands in relation R to y , or Ks exists *iff* Ks are mind-independent/posited by the best scientific theory. By contrast, deflationists claim that these properties do not have a deep nature and hold that the relevant concept of truth, reference or existence can be grasped only by certain trivial platitudes that govern the concept.

This paper primarily focuses on five kinds of deflationism: truth deflationism, syntacticism, fact/property expression deflationism, fact/property deflationism and existence deflationism. Truth deflationism argues that the property of truth has no deep nature that can be informative analyzed in terms of, e.g., correspondence to reality. ~~It is not possible to construct philosophical theories that provide informative biconditionals about truth.~~ All that can be said about truth is a relatively trivial and uninformative platitude which captures the meaning of ‘truth’:

(TD): ‘p is true’ = p

Syntacticism is a deflationary/minimalist conception of truth-conditionality (or truth-aptness), according to which there are two minimal requirements for truth-conditionality: the sentence (i) must be significant and (ii) declarative/indicative in form (see Boghossian 1990: 163-164).¹

Burgess, in his discussion of Boghossian’s “The Status of Content” (1990), distinguishes between deflationism about properties and deflationism about property expression, which are often mistakenly conflated. Property deflationism, which exists in the metaphysics of properties, claims that properties do not have substantive or deep nature that can be theorized about in terms of being mind-independent, physical, observable, and so on. Instead, the following equivalence schema exhausts the meaning of ‘property’:

(PD): The property of being P exists *iff* ‘P’ expresses (where ‘p’ is a meaningful predicate) (cf. Burgess 2010, 444).

On the other hand, deflationism about property expression is akin to reference deflationism. Reference deflationism argues that the property of reference has no deep nature that can be informative analyzed in terms of, e.g., causal relations. All that can be said reference is a relatively trivial and uninformative platitude which captures the meaning of ‘reference’:

(RD): P refers to x *iff* p=x (see Horwich 1998, 119).

Analogously, property expression deflationism argues that what it is for a predicate to refer is for a certain property to exist. Thus, there is no more to say about the reference of property expressions than the following relatively trivial and uninformative platitude:

(PED): ‘P’ expresses *iff* the property of being P exists (where ‘p’ is a predicate)

Thus, while property deflationists ground facts about property existence in the facts about predicate reference, property expression deflationists ground facts about predicate reference in facts about property existence.²

Resorting to Burgess work (2010, 444-445), I wish to distinguish between fact deflationism and fact expression deflationism in order to make sense of the work of

¹ According to Boghossian (1990: 163-164), on this deflationary conception of what it to possess truth conditions there is no space for semantic non-factualism or moral non-cognitivism.

² There is no reason to suspect that reference deflationism entails existence deflationism or *viceversa* (See Marschall & Schindler Forthcoming; cf. Thomasson 2013; 2014). Moreover, Burgess (2010, 445) explains that these positions are inconsistent, since “whatever this notion of grounding amounts to in the end, it will presumably be asymmetric in the sense that, if A grounds B then B can’t also ground A”.

Lovibond and Brandhorst. The former claims that facts do not have substantive or deep nature that can be theorized about in terms of being mind-independent, physical, observable, and so on. Instead, the following equivalence schema exhausts the meaning of ‘fact’:

(FD): The fact F exists *iff* ‘F’ expresses (where ‘F’ is a meaningful proposition).

Meanwhile, the latter claims that what it is for a proposition to refer is for a certain fact to exist. Thus, there is no more to say about the reference of propositions than the following equivalence schema:

(FED): ‘F’ expresses *iff* the fact F exists (where ‘F’ is a proposition).

Finally, existence deflationism is metaphysically deflationary about *all* entities, not just facts or properties (see Thomasson 2014 for a detailed explanation).³ “On this deflationary view, we should thus give up the search for some ‘criterion of existence’ telling us what it is for something to exist, just as semantic deflationists give up the search for the nature of reference, meaning or truth” (Thomasson 2014, 196-197). There is no substantive across-the-board criterion for existence in terms of having causal powers, being mind-independent, being physical, being observable and so on.

Since there is no substantive property of existence to be discovered, arguments about whether or not controversial entities exist are brought into question, as they are based on these entities lacking a property such as causal powers, mind-independence, physicality and so on. Thus, it is no longer metaphysically controversial to affirm the existence of certain entities, e.g., numbers, moral values, fictional characters, which have troubled ontologists during the past decades because they can be inferred from undisputed claims –albeit at the expense of making our ontology more promiscuous. For instance, from true propositions, e.g., ‘the house is red’ or ‘five is odd’, it is possible to infer that houses (and redness) and the number five (and an odd thing) exist (cf. Thomasson 2014, 185-197).

2. Lovibond and Brandhorst on Wittgenstein, Deflationism and Meta-ethics

The attribution of deflationism to Wittgenstein is not a novel claim among Wittgenstein scholars. Many have identified connections between Wittgenstein’s remarks on truth and truth deflationism (see Connelly 2013 and Bartunek 2019 for a detailed discussion). Furthermore, at first glance, the attribution of deflationism do not seem far-fetched, given Wittgenstein’s total rejection of philosophical dogmatism and philosophical theories (see e.g. PI, §11, §38, §119, §124-133). Brandhorst and Lovibond have sought to exploit this link between Wittgenstein’s later philosophy and deflationism in order to shed some light on the meta-ethical implications of his later moral philosophy.

2.1. Lovibond

³ Existence deflationism, as it is understood here, entails fact deflationism and property deflationism –albeit the inverse does not hold. Existence deflationism is often linked to meta-ontological deflationism and easy ontology, but I will not consider these latter proposals here (see Thomasson 2014; Marschall & Schindler Forthcoming for a discussion).

Lovibond (1983) has argued that Wittgenstein's embrace of deflationism offers a new way of understanding moral realism.⁴ On her interpretation, Wittgenstein's later philosophy propounds a seamless or a homogeneous conception of language, "free from invidious comparisons between different regions of discourse, or (relatedly) between different aspects of mental activity" (Lovibond 1983: 25). On this view, on the one hand, all sentences which are (i) meaningful and (ii) qualify by grammatical standards as propositions, i.e. they are declarative/indicative in form, *are* propositions that must be treated as descriptive, fact-stating and truth-apt (Lovibond 1983: 25-27). Wittgenstein, consequently, embodies syntacticism, a deflationary conception of truth-aptness.

On the other hand, all regions of assertoric discourse irrespective of content and subject-matter, embody the same relation between language and reality: the metaphysically neutral idea of 'talking about something' (Lovibond 1983: 26).⁵ The descriptive function of language is no longer confined to those parts of discourse that deal with natural or scientific subject-matters. For instance, declarative/indicative moral sentences qualify by grammatical standards as propositions and, thereby, are to be treated as descriptive, fact-stating and truth-apt propositions (Lovibond 1983: 27). There is no intelligible distinction between those parts of assertoric discourse that do genuinely describe reality and those which do not.

The homogeneity of assertoric discourse, then, is also affirmed at a metaphysical level, the level where empiricists draw a line between fact and value. Wittgenstein's seamless conception of language denies any metaphysical role to the idea of 'reality' to prevent the moral anti-realist from using the notion 'reality' as a peg on which to hang his or her special treatment of moral statements. ~~"Philosophical considerations cannot discredit the way in which we classify linguistic entities for other, non philosophical purposes" (Lovibond 1983, 26). This is an instance of the principle that "if words such as 'language', 'experience', 'world', have a use, it must be as humble a one as that of the words 'table', 'lamp' and 'door'" (PI, I §97). "The 'humility' in question here consists in an absence of metaphysical pretension" (Lovibond 1983: 36-37).~~

Value is thus reabsorbed into the real world from which the anti-realists and non-cognitivists expelled it. "Fact' and 'value' (in the metaphysical sense of those words) coalesce -and assertoric discourse is now seen to accommodate both impartially" (Lovibond 1983: 27). Reference to an objective reality is a target that is hit by *all* sentences that display the appropriate grammatical syntax. The only way in which declarative/indicative moral sentences can fail to describe reality is by *not being true*. In other words: Wittgenstein embodies a deflationary conception of existence and, by extension, facts and properties (Lovibond seemingly suggests that this is a natural consequence of Wittgenstein's syntacticism). Thus, from the true moral proposition 'John is good' it is possible to infer that John, the property of goodness and the fact that John

⁴ Moral realism, moral descriptivism and moral cognitivism are oftend conflated. Moral realism is a thesis in ontology about the existence of moral facts, properties or objects. Moral descriptivism is a thesis in semantics according to which moral language describes (or intends to describe) the world truthfully. Finally, moral cognitivism is constituted by a semantic thesis and a psychological thesis. The semantic thesis, i.e., semantic factualism, states that moral sentences are in the business of predicating properties and/or making statements that are apt for truth and falsity. The psychological thesis, i.e. psychological cognitivism, states that moral sentences express beliefs or other cognitive mental states. At times moral cognitivism also includes a third epistemological thesis about the existence of ethical knowledge. Although it is common for philosophers to defend all three positions simultaneously, it is important to understand that all three positions are independent. For instance, one may defend moral cognitivism despite rejecting moral realism, as is the case with error theorists.

⁵ Lovibond also seems to interpret Wittgenstein as a reference deflationist. I will not discuss the adequacy of this exegetical claim here.

exhibits the property of goodness exist.

According to Lovibond, Wittgenstein's remarks on language and philosophical method also lead to "a non-foundational epistemology which displays the notions of objectivity (sound judgement) and rationality (valid reasoning) as grounded in *consensus*" (Lovibond 1983: 40).⁶ This "makes it possible again to take a rationalist view of morals and politics, without having to revert to a pre-scientific attitude of mind in order to do so" (Lovibond 1983: 45-46). It is incorrect to assume, therefore, that there is a substantial metaphysical difference between scientific knowledge, rationality and objectivity, and ethical knowledge, rationality and objectivity. They are both entitled to the same consideration and status.

Wittgenstein's seamless conception of language in conjunction with his non-foundational epistemology and non-transcendent understanding of rationality changes our perspective towards a plausible and non-mystificatory moral realism. "Far from discrediting the critical concepts, allows them to penetrate again into the various regions of discourse from which empiricism has banished them" (Lovibond 1983: 45-46). Wittgenstein provides a metaphysically unexciting way of talking about facts, properties, truth and objectivity in ethics.

2.2. Brandhorst

Brandhorst (2015; 2017) has argued that Wittgenstein's embrace of deflationism offers a new way of understanding moral facts, which differs from, and avoids the objectivist commitments of, moral realism. Brandhorst's proposed interpretation stems from an attempt to make sense of the following quote from Wittgenstein's discussions on ethics with Rush Rhees:

The way in which some reality corresponds – or conflicts – with a physical theory has no counterpart here [in ethics]" (Rhees 1965, 24 my brackets).

On Brandhorst's interpretation Wittgenstein is not discarding the idea of ethical facts. Instead, he is deflating this notion in order to provide a view apart from those 'realist' theories on ethics that mistakenly attempt to establish substantial analogies between ethics and natural sciences.

The basis of Brandhorst's proposed interpretation is Wittgenstein's embodiment of a deflationist conception of truth.⁷ Wittgenstein, in his conversations with Rush Rhees (1965, 24), deflates the notion of ethical truth "by tying it to a subjective, personal point of view" (Brandhorst 2015, 247). His endorsement of truth deflationism is epitomized by his use of the equivalence schema: "remember that '*p* is true' means simply '*p*'" (Rhees 1965, 24). "This is consistent with other discussions of truth in the later work, and it embodies what is now known as a deflationary conception of truth" (Brandhorst 2015, 231; see PI §136-137; Wittgenstein, Rhees & Citron 2015, 29; RFM §117; for other examples of Wittgenstein's use of this equivalence schema).

Brandhorst explains that with this deflationary conception of truth Wittgenstein obtains a deflationary conception of facts. "Instead of saying that *p* is true, we can also say that it is a fact that *p*, the concepts 'truth' and 'fact' were made for each other"

⁶ Lovibond's interpretation of objectivity and rationality in Wittgenstein's later work does not seem to differ substantially from McDowell's (1998; 2002) interpretation. However, McDowell resorts to the notions rule-following and forms of life to substantiate the claim that Wittgenstein provides a new way of understanding moral realism and moral cognitivism.

⁷ In this paper I will not discuss the adequacy of interpreting Wittgenstein as truth deflationist (see Vision 2005; Connelly 2013; Bartunek 2019 for a discussion on Wittgenstein and truth deflationism).

(Brandhorst 2015, 232) –“if there are truths, there are facts” (Brandhorst 2015, 233). Thus, we obtain the following equivalence schema:

(BFD): ‘ p is fact’ means simply ‘ p ’.

Unfortunately, Brandhorst’s initial characterization of fact deflationism and its equivalence schema is lack-luster, since it does not drive or deliver the ontological conclusion he desires, i.e. that Wittgenstein is positing the existence of deflated moral facts. The equivalence schema invoked by Brandhorst specifies the meaning of ‘fact’ when used as a logico-linguistic tool in natural language. In other words, this schema delivers a semantic conclusion about ‘fact’, not an ontological conclusion about facts. Thus, in what follows I will describe Brandhorst’s proposed interpretation by resorting to the deflationist conception of facts presented in section 1.

The point Brandhorst is trying to make in his work is that when we state something is the case we do not “stop anywhere short of the fact” (PI, §95). For instance, the true assertion of an ethical proposition does not stop anywhere short of a moral fact. Wittgenstein, then, has abandoned his earlier views about the non-existence of moral facts by recognizing that talk of facts has no metaphysical depth and that their existence can be simply inferred from true moral propositions (Brandhorst 2015, 232-233).

Brandhorst adduces further evidence for his interpretation in Wittgenstein’s abandonment of his earlier idea that there are no logical and mathematical facts.⁸ In mathematics and logic expressions like “ $2+2=4$ ” or “ $\neg\neg p \Rightarrow p$ ” can be used to express propositions that are either true or false.⁹ When true, these propositions do not stop anywhere short of mathematical and logical facts respectively. “In this respect, ethical, logical and mathematical sentences are on a par with ‘snow is white’ or ‘it is raining’” (Brandhorst 2015, 233).

Brandhorst, in consequence, interprets Wittgenstein as propounding a deflationary conception of facts, according to which:

(FD) A fact x exists *iff* ‘ p ’ expresses x (where ‘ p ’ is a meaningful proposition).

Thus, from true moral, logical and mathematical propositions it is possible to infer the existence of moral, logical and mathematical facts, albeit these concessions have no metaphysical depth since they are understood as facts in a *thin*, attenuated sense.

I believe Brandhorst’s work would have substantially benefited from including a discussion about property deflationism and existence deflationism. On the one hand, ontological debates in meta-ethics primarily focus on whether moral values are to be

⁸ Brandhorst exploits parallels between ethics and mathematics to uphold his proposal, but fails to justify why this is a legitimate exegetical strategy. Wittgenstein rarely discusses ethics in connection to mathematics in his later work and there is no instance where explicitly draws a parallel between both of them. ~~These issues are accentuated when we inspect Wittgenstein’s remarks on the relation between mathematical propositions and reality. For instance, he explains that mathematical propositions, e.g., ‘ $2+2=4$ ’, do not denote a certain fact or object that is part of the fabric of the world. Instead, they are rules for constructing empirical propositions that do denote a fact, e.g., ‘If Brown has two apples and Jones gives him two apples, Brown has four apples (see Diamond 1996 for a detailed discussion). There seems to be no parallel explanation for ethics. Moral propositions, i.e. ascriptions of moral value, are not akin to mathematical propositions. Treating them as such may raise certain concerns that are much more troubling than Brandhorst suspects. The only commonality they share is that they involve entities whose ontology is controversial.~~

⁹ Note that Brandhorst (2015, 233) interprets Wittgenstein as endorsing syntacticism.

understood as properties/qualities or not, as both Wittgenstein (see MWL, 318-319, 332-333; AWL §§31-32) and Brandhorst (2015, 246) recognize.

On the other hand, Brandhorst does not limit his ontological claims about mathematics and ethics to the existence of facts. He also discusses the existence (in a deflationary sense) of objects (Brandhorst 2015, 235, 239-240), properties (Brandhorst 2015, 235, 245), numbers (Brandhorst 2015, 239-240), values (Brandhorst 2015, 245) and so on. Definitely, on Brandhorst's (2015, 243) interpretation, "a reality corresponds not only to propositions if they are true, but also to words such as 'two', 'red', 'rain' or 'perhaps'". Thus, he implicitly interprets Wittgenstein as an existence and property deflationist to uphold these ontological claims, since fact deflationism alone cannot deliver them –the existence of facts does not entail the existence of other entities.

Having detailed the ontological implications of Wittgenstein's embrace of deflationism, Brandhorst returns to the quote presented at the start of this section, which is the focal point of his paper. On Brandhorst's interpretation, Wittgenstein is not denying that there is a sense in which moral judgments can be said to be true and correspond to moral facts. Instead, he is suggesting that ethical truths and facts are substantially disanalogous to physical ones.¹⁰ Both moral judgments and physical judgments "can be described as judgments of fact, and the interesting further question is how reference to some 'reality' enters the picture. This marks the place [...] where his deflationist view of 'truth' and 'fact' comes to the fore" (Brandhorst 2015, 234)

On the one hand, physical judgments (or judgments of fact) refer to facts, in some thick, robust sense of 'fact', and are *objectively* true or false in virtue of the objective and mind-independent facts to which they correspond. Thus, there is an independent and observable reality that can be used to substantiate the truth of a physical judgment by being just as the judgment says it is, independently of human inclinations (Brandhorst 2015, 236). For instance, suppose a physical theory claims that gold has better conductivity than silver. If this judgment is true it is because it represents the way things really are in the world with respect to conductivity. Reality can be measured and modeled in the appropriate ways to settle its truth or falsity.

On the other hand, moral judgments refer to facts, in some thin attenuated and deflated sense of 'fact', and are *not objectively* true or false in virtue of some objective and mind-independent facts to which they correspond. This is due to the fact that there is no mind-independent and objective reality that can be used to substantiate the truth of a moral judgment by being just as the judgment says it is. Instead, moral judgments are true or false in light of our personal commitments and attitudes –remember: on Brandhorst's view Wittgenstein *deflates* truth in ethics by tying it to a personal, subjective point of view.

Thus, summarizing, Wittgenstein's ontological and epistemological concessions with regards to ethics have no metaphysical depth and do not deliver the objectivism required for moral realism.¹¹ While truths and facts do have a rightful place in ethics, "they come into the picture in an entirely different way than many traditional ethical

¹⁰ Although much of Brandhorst's discussion focuses on two kinds of correspondence, the differences in correspondence are grounded in the reality to which propositions correspond, not the relation of correspondence itself -whose nature is unclear as Brandhorst says little about it. In other words: the differences between ethical correspondence and physical correspondence are a consequence of the substantial differences between moral and physical facts. Thus, it seems more appropriate to speak of two kinds of reality to which things can correspond, instead of two kinds of correspondence.

¹¹ Although Wittgenstein's remarks on truth and facts do not suffice to deliver moral realism, I believe that on Brandhorst's interpretation Wittgenstein is to be understood as loosely committed to moral descriptivism and moral cognitivism. Despite the non-existence of objective moral truths and moral facts, it is still possible to speak of deflated moral facts and moral truths that correspondence to moral judgments.

theories encourage us to think they do” (Brandhorst 2015, 245). Wittgenstein’s target in his conversations with Rhees is not the idea of an ethical reality or truth, but rather the claim to objectivity that characterizes moral realism.¹² Moral realists get it wrong from the outset by modeling moral truths and facts on the realist picture described with regards to physical judgments and theories. A similar problem is raised by Wittgenstein against Platonists, who misconstrue numbers and mathematical facts as being substantially analogous to physical objects and facts (see Brandhorst 2015, 242-243).

3. Moral entities

Both Brandhorst and Lovibond claim that Wittgenstein’s embrace of deflationism provides us with a deflationary and metaphysical unexciting way of speaking about moral facts, properties, objects and other entities. ~~On this view, the existence of moral entities is simply inferred from the assertion of true moral propositions.~~ Throughout the remainder of this paper I set out argue that the attribution of deflationism does not do justice to Wittgenstein’s later work and it is concluded, therefore, that the appeal to deflationism does not afford or substantiate the exegetical claims made by Lovibond and Brandhorst. First, I discuss some inconsistencies in Brandhorst’s characterization of fact deflationism as a *local* position. Second, I argue that, while these inconsistencies are solved by Lovibond’s interpretation, the proposed solution fails to capture the intricacies of Wittgenstein’s later work. Thirdly, I examine Wittgenstein’s remarks on the ontology of moral values and grammar of moral discourse, largely ignored by Brandhorst and Lovibond, in order to make plain that there is insufficient textual evidence to uphold their exegetical claims.

4. Local fact deflationism?

Despite the centrality of deflationism to Brandhorst’s proposed interpretation, he is unable to spell out its implications and, therefore, misconstrues this philosophical program throughout various points in his paper. A clear-cut example is to be found in the distinction he makes between moral, mathematical and logical facts and, on the other hand, empirical facts. The latter describes facts in a robust, thick sense of ‘fact’: they are objective, real, observable and mind-independent facts. The former, conversely, describe facts in a thin, attenuated and deflated sense of ‘fact’: they have no metaphysical depth the nature of which can be analyzed in terms of mind-independence, observability or objectivity. This difference is attested by the inevitable failure of any attempt to establish substantial analogies between these two senses of fact (Brandhorst 2015, 241-242).

On Brandhorst’s interpretation, then, Wittgenstein is a *local* fact deflationist: fact deflationism is only true of some facts (e.g., moral, mathematical and logical facts), not all of them (e.g., empirical or physical facts). In other words: There are both harmless empty facts as the *deflationist* conceives them (see Brandhorst 2015, 245) and substantial

¹² De Mesel has objected “that Brandhorst’s arguments actually support a case *for* objectivity in Wittgensteinian ethics rather than a case *against* it” (De Mesel 2017, 41). Objectivity need not involve reference to an impersonal and ethically neutral standard. “An objective judgement is not one that is *uninformed* by feeling or personal attitudes or commitments or outlooks, but one which is *undistorted* by them” (De Mesel 2017, 46). Brandhorst misconstrues objectivity on a Platonist picture, which requires a view from nowhere, a neutral and impersonal standpoint. Brandhorst takes pains to argue that notions such as truth, fact or correspondence do not require metaphysical depth and that they do not have to be distorted by this Platonist picture, but he overlooks that the same may hold for objectivity. Brandhorst (2017, 64), in response to De Mesel’s paper, has upheld and reinforced his claim that Wittgenstein rules out the idea of objectivity in ethics as the realist conceives it, since it requires *both* substantial truth and objectivity in ethics. For more on this discussion see De Mesel (2017) and Brandhorst (2017).

objective mind-independent facts as the *objectivist* conceives them (see Brandhorst 2015, 236, 245).

In drawing this distinction, Brandhorst misconstrues fact deflationism and, thereby, fails to recognize that this philosophical program is not well suited for the exegetical claims he is advancing in his paper. Fact deflationism is a *global* philosophical program according to which all that can be said about *all* facts is the metaphysically unexciting trivial schema FD. *All* facts are understood as something thin or unsubstantial: a shadow casted by meaningful propositions. They do not have a substantive or deep nature that can be theorized about and informatively analyzed in terms of being mind-independent, physical, observable, and so on.

Thus, fact deflationism is inconsistent with Brandhorst's distinction between thin facts (with a shallow nature) and thick facts (with a deep nature). On the one hand, the characterization of empirical facts he attributes to Wittgenstein betrays the central claim of fact deflationism. On Brandhorst's interpretation, Wittgenstein accepts that physical facts do have a deep nature that can be informatively analyzed in terms of mind-independence and objectivity. Thus, he accepts something more than it is allowed by fact deflationism.

On the deflationist view all facts are to be understood as thin or unsubstantial facts that lack a deep nature. There can be no facts whose nature is substantially disanalogous to these deflated facts. In other words: there is no room for anything other than deflated facts. Facts come into play in one way and one way only. Thus, not only is a mistake to conceive moral facts as substantial, objective and mind-independent facts insofar it posits mysterious entities with a 'shadowy' existence (Brandhorst 215, 245): it is a mistake to conceive any fact as such, including empirical ones.

On the other hand, the distinction he attributes to Wittgenstein between different kinds of facts on the basis of them having a substantially disanalogous nature also betrays the central claim of deflationism. According to Brandhorst's (2015, 233), Wittgenstein rejects a "single overarching 'theory' of facts" in favor of recognizing a plurality of local 'theories', each one providing a detailed explanation for different kinds of facts which cannot be regarded as substantially analogous.¹³

On the deflationist view all that can be said about facts is exhausted by the relatively trivial platitude FD. This equivalence schema does not warrant a distinction between different kinds of facts, such as the one Brandhorst identifies in Wittgenstein's later philosophy between harmless empty moral facts and substantive objective mind-independent physical facts, because facts are no more than shadows casted by true propositions. Thus, there is no substantial nature to facts that affords drawing said distinction, as it requires something more substantial and informative than the deflationist is willing to concede.

Note that I am not arguing against the legitimacy of interpreting Wittgenstein as endorsing a distinction between different kinds of facts or realities whose nature is substantially disanalogous. My point is that this exegetical claim is inconsistent with the attribution of fact deflationism. Brandhorst misconstrues Wittgenstein as both a substantialist and insubstantialist (i.e. deflationist) about facts, thereby ignoring that these philosophical programs are contradictory and inconsistent. Hence why a deflationary conception of facts is not well suited for Brandhorst's exegetical purposes.

¹³ Note that the deflationist's concern with a single overarching theory of facts is the use of a metaphysical theory. Rejecting a single overarching theory of facts in favor of a plurality of theories does not solve this problem, but rather multiplies it.

By recognizing that fact deflationism is a *global* philosophical program that reduces all philosophical talk about facts to the trivial platitude FD, Brandhorst is faced with an exegetical choice. He can either maintain the claim that Wittgenstein is a fact deflationist, thereby abandoning the distinction between moral and physical facts or, alternatively, he can maintain the claim that Wittgenstein distinguishes between moral and physical facts, thereby abandoning the attribution of fact deflationism. I believe that the latter option is more in line with Brandhorst's proposed interpretation.¹⁴ Nevertheless, the purpose of this paper is to examine the legitimacy of attributing deflationism to Wittgenstein in order to make sense of his later views in meta-ethics. In consequence, only the former option will be discussed here.

5. Fact, property and existence deflationism

In order to evaluate the adequacy of interpreting Wittgenstein as a fact deflationist it is convenient to discuss the work of Sabina Lovibond. On Lovibond's interpretation, Wittgenstein is a deflationist about existence and, by extension, facts and properties. He provides us with a metaphysical unexciting way of speaking about reality where reference to an objective reality is a target that is hit by *all* sentences that display the grammatical syntax of a declarative/sentence. Thus, from true propositions it is possible to infer the existence of different entities such as facts, properties or objects. For instance, from the true moral proposition 'John is good' it is possible to infer that John, the property of goodness and the fact that John exhibits the property of goodness exist. The only way in which declarative/indicative moral sentences can fail to describe reality is by *not being true*.

Despite the centrality of this exegetical claim to Lovibond's attribution of moral realism to Wittgenstein, she fails to offer textual evidence to substantiate it.¹⁵ Lovibond takes existence deflationism (and, by extension, fact and property deflationism) to be an integral part of Wittgenstein's seamless conception of language and, thereby, a consequence of his commitment to syntacticism. That is, by offering a seamless conception of language, which takes declarative/indicative syntactical form as a sufficient condition for truth-aptness and propositionhood, Wittgenstein denies any metaphysical role to the idea of 'reality', thus preventing the moral anti-realist from using the notion 'reality' as a peg on which to hang his or her special treatment of moral statements.

It is a mistake, however, to construe syntacticism as entailing a commitment to existence, fact or property deflationism. The former is a semantic/epistemological claim about the truth-aptness of sentences, while the latter are metaphysical claims about existence, facts and properties. Although their combination may prove beneficial, there

¹⁴ It is unclear why Brandhorst appeals to deflationism in order to explain how moral and mathematical judgments differ from empirical judgments with regards to their correspondence to reality. According to Brandhorst (2015, 243; LFM, 247), stating that a reality corresponds to moral and mathematical propositions simply means that "we have some use for them", not that they denote some observable entity in the world. Notwithstanding the specifics of this proposed interpretation, there seems to be no recognizable connection with fact deflationism. Brandhorst himself implicitly recognizes the futility of his appeal to fact deflationism in sections VII and VIII of his paper, where he fleshes out his proposed interpretation of the reality to which mathematical and ethical propositions correspond. In neither section does he reference or allude to fact deflationism, which is only briefly discussed in section III, thus raising questions about the point of introducing fact deflationism in the first place.

¹⁵ The only textual evidence adduced by Lovibond is to be found in §97 of the *Investigations*. There Wittgenstein notes that "if words such as 'language', 'experience', 'world', have a use, it must be as humble a one as that of the words 'table', 'lamp' and 'door'" (PI, I §97). "The 'humility' in question here consists in an absence of metaphysical pretension" (Lovibond 1983: 36-37). However, the absence of metaphysical pretensions or philosophical theories need not entail a commitment to deflationism. There are other ways of embracing insubstantialism and quietism without endorsing deflationism.

is no reason to suspect that syntacticism alone *entails* existence, fact or property deflationism (or *viceversa*) without the appeal to further commitments. For instance, an error theorist may hold syntacticism in conjunction with a non-deflationary theory of facts (and a correspondence theory of truth), thus allowing him or her to explain that meaningful declarative moral sentences are truth-apt but are always false because there are no mind-independent moral facts to make them true.

Lovibond, in consequence, must provide further arguments and explanations to substantiate the attribution of existence, fact and property deflationism to Wittgenstein – especially if she is willing to uphold her claim that Wittgenstein is a moral realist.

5.1. Lectures on the Foundations on Mathematics

The textual evidenced adduced by Brandhorst does not fare much better because it is self-defeating. Specifically, it highlights some of Wittgenstein's later remarks on mathematics which are inconsistent with existence, fact and property deflationism.

In *Lectures on the Foundations of Mathematics* Wittgenstein provides a detailed discussion about the kind of reality to which mathematics corresponds. One of the recurrent themes in these lectures is the temptation to Platonist views, which model mathematical reality analogously to physical reality. As Brandhorst (2015, 239-242) rightly points out, Wittgenstein rejects these Platonist views on the basis that the analogy they employ is unintelligible and “extremely misleading” (LFM, 240). By contrast, Wittgenstein developed the idea of an enormous difference between reality corresponding to experiential propositions and reality corresponding to mathematical propositions (see Diamond 1996, Connelly 2013 and Brandhorst 2015 for further discussion).

Take, for instance, the propositions ‘2 is even’ and ‘The sofa is green’. Platonists, among other philosophers, tend to construe these propositions as being about the world in exactly the same sense. That is, they are both propositions that (if true) denote a fact where an object (the number two and a sofa respectively) exemplifies a property (evenness and greenness respectively). Wittgenstein sets out to question this view by describing the muddle it gets us in. Initially he examines the use of the words ‘two’ and ‘sofa’.

If we were asked to explain what the reality is which corresponds to "two", we should not know what to say.-This? [He indicated the two fingers.] But isn't it also six, or four? We have certain words such that if we were asked, "What is the reality which corresponds?", we should all point to the same thing -for example, "sofa", "green", etc. But "perhaps", "and", "or", "two", "plus" ... are quite different. (LFM, 248)

Being clear about the difference between ‘two’ and ‘sofa’ amounts to understanding that the mathematical proposition is about numbers in the sense that it helps prepare the number-sign for its applications, not that the reality corresponding to the mathematical proposition amounts to some sort of realm of numbers (Diamond 1996, 336). As Wittgenstein puts it:

If you have a mathematical proposition about No, and you imagine you are talking about a realm of numbers, -I would reply that you aren't as yet talking about a realm of anything, in the most important sense of "about". You are only giving rules for the use of "No". (LFM, 251)

When ‘two’ is asserted in a mathematical proposition it does not denote or affirm the

existence of the number 2 as an object that is part of reality. Although it is clear that mathematical propositions are about numbers, if you are not clear about the specific sense in which they are about numbers then you “are almost sure to be in a muddle. Because you don't see that what is about 2 in the sense in which a proposition is about a sofa, is never a mathematical proposition” (LFM, 251).

Thus, contrary to existence deflationists, Wittgenstein does not infer the existence of numbers from true mathematical propositions. Furthermore, if he did infer their existence, it is evident by his critique of the Platonist views that the kind of existence that pertains to mathematical objects is disanalogous to that of empirical objects. For instance, the former are the result of human invention while the latter are the result of empirical discovery (see RFM, I-168, II-2, II-38, V-9, VII-5). The description of this difference entails accepting something more than it is allowed by existence deflationist: the use of a criterion of existence telling us what it is for something to exist, e.g. human invention, observability and so on (cf. Thomasson 2014, 196-197).

Wittgenstein extends his remarks on ‘two’ and ‘sofa’ to differentiate the realities that correspond to true mathematical propositions, e.g. ‘two is even’, and true empirical propositions, e.g. ‘the sofa is green’. The latter denote facts in which objects exemplify properties. For instance, ‘the sofa is green’ denotes the fact in which a sofa exemplifies the property of greenness. Meanwhile, mathematical propositions are not about the world insofar as they denote mathematical facts where mathematical objects exemplify mathematical properties. For instance, ‘two is even’ does not denote a fact in which the number two exemplifies the property of evenness.

By contrast, mathematical propositions are about reality insofar as they are preparations for a use of language: they prepare number-signs for their application. To say a reality corresponds to ‘two is even’ “is like saying ‘A reality corresponds to ‘two’.’ It is like saying a reality corresponds to a rule, which would come to saying: ‘It is a useful rule, most useful -we couldn't do without it for a thousand reasons, not just one’” (LFM, 249).

Thus, against fact deflationists, Wittgenstein does not infer the existence of mathematical facts from true mathematical propositions. Furthermore, if he did infer their existence, it is evident by his critique of the Platonist views that mathematical facts are substantially disanalogous to empirical ones. The description of this difference entails accepting that facts are not merely shadows casted by true propositions, which is something more than it is allowed by fact deflationism.

Although Wittgenstein does not discuss the difference between mathematical predicates (e.g. ‘even’) and empirical predicates (e.g. ‘green’) in these passages of the *Lectures on the Foundations of Mathematics*, it seems reasonable to assume that he would offer a similar conclusion. Empirical predicates denote properties that are predicated about objects. For instance, in ‘The sofa is green’, the predicate ‘green’ denotes the property of greenness which is predicated about the sofa. Meanwhile, mathematical predicates are about numbers in the sense that they help prepare number-signs for their applications, not that they correspond to mathematical properties that are predicated about mathematical objects.

Thus, against property deflationists, Wittgenstein does not infer the existence of mathematical properties from meaningful mathematical predicates. Furthermore, if he did infer their existence, it is evident by his critique of the Platonist views that mathematical properties are substantially disanalogous to empirical ones. The description of this difference entails accepting that properties are not merely shadows casted by meaningful predicates, which is something more than it is allowed by property deflationism.

Summarizing, Wittgenstein’s remarks on mathematics are inconsistent with

existence, fact and property deflationism. Despite recognizing the existence of true mathematical propositions, Wittgenstein explains through his critique of Platonist views that mathematical propositions do not warrant the postulation of mathematical entities that are akin to those empirical entities that are denoted by true empirical propositions. What ontological status Wittgenstein adjudicates to mathematics and mathematical entities remains a controversial topic among Wittgenstein scholars. However, this exegetical puzzle and the indeterminacy of its solution pose no threat to the present paper.

On the one hand, if “there is no putative realm of mathematical objects the reality of which either to affirm (realism) or to deny (anti-realism)” (Connelly 2013, 576), then mathematical facts, objects and properties cannot be inferred from true mathematical propositions. Thus, against Brandhorst and Lovibond, it is mistake to attribute existence, fact and property deflationism to Wittgenstein.

On the other hand, if mathematical entities are to be inferred from true mathematical propositions, Wittgenstein’s critique of Platonist views makes it plain that these entities are substantially disanalogous to empirical ones. Note that Wittgenstein’s objection against the Platonist is not the model or picture they take from physics, but rather its application to mathematics. In other words: Wittgenstein’s dislike of the Platonists analogy is not due to it presenting a erroneous picture of empirical reality, but rather mistakenly construing and modeling mathematical reality in accordance with this picture.

Conceding that mathematical entities exist does not afford the attribution of existence, fact and property deflationism, because said concession *must* entail a substantial distinctiveness with regards to empirical entities. As explained above, for Wittgenstein it is a mistake to construe and model mathematical reality analogously to physical reality. Once you get clear about the reality to which mathematical propositions correspond, you recognize that ‘Two is even’ is not about mathematical objects and properties in the same way as ‘The sofa is green’ is about empirical objects and properties. Instead, “you will look for the reality corresponding to it in an entirely different place; not in mathematics but in its application” (LFM, 251).

The description of this difference is inconsistent with and entails accepting something more than it is allowed by existence, fact and property deflationism. On the deflationist’s view, there is no more to existence, facts and properties than what relatively uninformative trivial platitudes say there is (see section 1). However, these platitudes do not afford the distinction Wittgenstein draws in his discussion with the Platonist. There he explains that the views of the Platonist rest on the mistaken assumption that mathematical entities are analogous to empirical ones. The description of this disanalogy entails accepting either that there are no mathematical entities or, alternatively, that they do exist but are substantially different from empirical ones. Notwithstanding the differences, neither option satisfies the deflationists demands. As Brandhorst (2015, 235 my brackets) puts it: “the formal and empty sense [of truth and facts] fails to yield the distinction that Wittgenstein draws”.

Granting Lovibond is right in claiming that, according to Wittgenstein, reference to reality is a target hit by *all* sentences that display the appropriate grammatical syntax, it is a mistake to interpret Wittgenstein as endorsing the claim that *all* regions of assertoric discourse, irrespective of content and subject-matter, are about reality in the same way. The idea of ‘talking about something’ (Lovibond 1983: 26) is more intricate than Lovibond suspects and does not afford the attribution of existence, fact and property deflationism. Against Lovinond (and Brandhorst), deflationism does not do justice to the intricacies of Wittgenstein’s philosophy of mathematics.

5.2. Mental state ascriptions

A similar problem can be raised against Lovibond and Brandhorst proposed interpretations by calling attention to Wittgenstein's remarks on psychology and mental state ascriptions. On Lovibond and Brandhorst's deflationist interpretation, Wittgenstein should be willing to accept that from true declarative psychological sentences, e.g., 'I am in pain' or 'John is in pain', one can infer the existence of psychological entities which are analogous to empirical entities. However, upon closer inspection, this exegetical claim seems contentious at best.

Wittgenstein accused the inner/outer conception of mistakenly assimilating the mental entities to physical ones. Specifically, "it construes the relationship between mental phenomena and mental terms 'on the model of material 'object and designation', and thereby turns the mind into a realm of mental entities, states, processes and events, which are just like their physical counterparts, only hidden and more ethereal (PI §293, §308, §339; BB, 47, 64, 70)" (Glock 1996, 53).

According to Wittgenstein, this distorted understanding of mental phenomena is partly rooted in the surface grammar of language, which encourages us to think that substantives always stand for substances, adjectives for properties, verbs for actions or states of being, and declarative sentences for facts (cf. MWL, 318-320; PI: p. 190; RPP I: §494; Z: §51; LA, Part I §3). In other words: it encourages, rather than forbids, using all linguistic expressions by analogy to those that are characteristic of factual/empirical discourse. Wittgenstein's remarks on psychological phenomena pose a threat to both Brandhorst and Lovibond's interpretations.

Wittgenstein explains that philosophers have traditionally established a parallel between psychological verbs and adjectives, e.g., 'believe' and 'pain' respectively, with denoting verbs and adjectives, e.g., 'cut' and 'hard' respectively. Since the latter describe observable processes (i.e. cutting) and properties (i.e. hardness), philosophers assume that psychological verbs and adjectives must also describe observable processes (i.e. believing) and properties (i.e. pain) (PI: p. 190; see also RPP I: §494; Z: §51; LA, Part I §3). Wittgenstein contends, however, that these psychological linguistic expressions do not denote observable processes or properties that are analogous to their physical counterparts.

Take, for instance, Wittgenstein's remarks on the distinctive grammar of first and second/third person mental state ascriptions. These mental state ascriptions generally make use of the word 'have' to ascribe such-and-such mental state to an individual, e.g. 'I have a headache', 'John has a headache' and 'John and Mary have a headache'. Due to their surface grammar, philosophy general models these mental state ascriptions by analogy to empirical sentences that have the same surface grammar, e.g., 'I have a book', 'John has a book' and 'John and Mary have a book'. It is customary, then, to understand 'have' as having the same meaning as 'own' and to treat the mental state as it were a physical entity that is being ascribed to an individual. Accordingly, philosophers take 'Someone has such-and-such mental state' to mean that they own that mental state in the same way the own a book.

As explained above, Wittgenstein contends that philosophy misconstrues these linguistic expressions due to their attempt to construe mental phenomenal and terms on the model of physical/material phenomena and designation. By doing so they fail to recognize that "the difference between 'I have it' & 'he has it' is not like that between 'it is in this place' & 'is in that place'" (MWL, 275). Wittgenstein describes another example of this mistake in his discussions on belief in *Remarks on the Philosophy of Psychology*. There he explains that the statement 'I believe that such and such is the case' does not describe a mental state or an observable process. Instead, this statement is equivalent to

the assertion ‘such and such is the case’ (RPP I: §472, §501).

Mental state ascriptions are not used to describe “a distribution in a space and time” (PI, ix), i.e. a state of affairs where an individual stands in relation to or exemplifies a psychological property, such as a mental state.¹⁶ If this were the case “it should be meaningful to ask about described event ‘when did it happen?’, ‘for how long did it happen?’, etc. Wittgenstein shows that these questions make no point when asked after some attributions of mental states” (Acero & Villanueva 2012, 105; for examples see PI §638-640 on intention, PI §11xi on ‘struck by’, PG §12 on understanding, Z §78 on hope, Z §286 on orders). To avoid construing mental phenomenal and terms on the model of material object and designation we would have to invent “a language in which we didn’t use ‘I have tooth-ache’ & ‘He has’: e.g. for first said “There is tooth-ache here”, & “He is behaving so & so”.” (MWL, 269). Note, again, that Wittgenstein does not oppose the philosopher’s model of material object and designation, but rather challenges their attempt to model mental phenomena on this picture.

Despite the existing controversies among Wittgenstein scholars about the ontological status he adjudicates to psychological phenomena, Wittgenstein’s negative claims about the implausibility of construing psychological phenomena on the model of physical entities suffice for our purposes here. Against fact and property deflationists, Wittgenstein does not infer the existence of psychological facts and properties from true psychological propositions and meaningful psychological respectively. Alternatively, if he did infer their existence, it is evident by his critique of the inner/outer conception that psychological facts and properties are substantially disanalogous to empirical ones. The description of this difference entails accepting that facts and properties are not merely shadows casted by true propositions and meaningful predicates, which is something more than it is allowed by fact and property deflationism.

Deflationism, then, does not do justice to the intricacies of Wittgenstein’s remarks on psychological phenomena. Despite his affinity to the deflationist’s rejection of philosophical theories that offer informative analyses of facts and properties, Wittgenstein opposes the idea that relatively trivial platitudes provide a complete and satisfactory description of the concepts of fact and property since they do not afford the distinction Wittgenstein draws between psychological and physical phenomena.

The problems described above also pose a threat to the attribution of existence deflationism to Wittgenstein. On this deflationary view, we should give up the search for some across-the-board criterion for existence in favor of recognizing that the existence of entities can simply be inferred from undisputed claims. Although Wittgenstein sympathizes with the rejection of philosophical theories that provide across-the-board criteria for existence, he seems unwilling to fully endorse the existence deflationist’s philosophical program.

On the one hand, if Wittgenstein denies the ontological existence of psychological phenomena, such as mental states, then it is patent that there are no entities to be inferred from true psychological propositions. On the other hand, if Wittgenstein concedes that psychological phenomena exist, his critique of the inner/outer conception makes it plain that psychological phenomena are substantially disanalogous to, and should not be

¹⁶ The inadequacy of construing mental phenomenal and terms on the model of physical/material phenomena and designation is further attested by Wittgenstein’s description of first mental state ascriptions as avowals. “Negatively, this indicates that they are not descriptions or reports of private mental entities encountered in an inner realm. Positively, Wittgenstein characterizes avowals as expressive in the way in which a gesture or frown expresses or manifests emotions, attitudes, etc. They are partial substitutes for, and learnt extensions of, natural expressions of the mental, such as cries, smiles or grimaces” (Glock 1996, 50).

modeled on the picture of, physical/observable phenomena. The description of this difference involves recognizing that criteria for the existence of psychological phenomena are distinct from those of observable physical phenomena. In other words: the description of this difference entails accepting a criterion of existence telling us what it is for something to exist, which is something more than it is allowed by existence deflationism.

The inadequacy of attributing existence deflationism to Wittgenstein can be attested solely by the differing grammars of first-person mental state ascriptions (e.g., ‘I have toothache’) and second (and third) person mental state ascriptions (e.g., ‘He has toothache’). For instance, it is sensible to ask, in the latter case, ‘How do I know this?’, but not in the former” (AWL, §18).

Wittgenstein (MWL, 267-270; AWL, §18) explains that the difference in their grammar is a direct consequence of the criteria invoked to verify the mental state in question. ‘I have toothache’ “I know directly; whether another does I only know from what he tells me & his behaviour” (MWL, 271). In other words: in the first case the verification of the existence of the mental state is known directly because “I feel it” (MWL, 276), while in the second case the criteria for the existence of the mental state is reliant on what others tell us or their behavior.¹⁷ Against existence deflationism, the explanation of this difference entails accepting different criteria telling us what it is for something to exist and verifying how we know such-and-such.

Furthermore, according to Wittgenstein (MWL, 269-271, 276), it is possible to invoke different criteria to verify the existence second/third-person mental states. At times our knowledge of someone having such-and-such mental state is the result of the behavior they exhibit. For instance, that John has toothache can be verified by John’s expressive behavior, e.g., he is screaming while holding his tooth (MWL, 269, 271). At other times the verification may be reliant on what he or she tells us (MWL, 271, 276). For instance, that John has toothache can be verified by the fact that John tells us that he had a toothache. Again, against existence deflationism, the explanation of this difference entails accepting different criteria telling us what it is for something to exist and verifying how we know such-and-such.

Definitely, there is a tendency to “confuse ‘I have a piece of chalk’ and ‘He has a piece of chalk’ with ‘I have an ache’ and ‘He has an ache’” (AWL, §18) and, thereby, assume that the verification of the second pair is analogous to that of the first pair. Wittgenstein contends, however, that not only is it clear that what is criterion for psychological phenomena is quite different from what is criterion for physical phenomena, but it is also “clear, & admitted that what verifies /is criterion for/ ‘I have tooth-ache’ is quite different from what verifies /criterion for/ ‘He has tooth-ache’” (MWL, 267). Thus, against existence deflationism, the explanation of the differences between (i) psychological and physical phenomena and (ii) first and second/third person mental states entails accepting distinct criteria of existence telling us what it is for something to exist, which is more than it is allowed by existence deflationism.

Another example of the inconsistencies that arise from the attribution of existence deflationism to Wittgenstein is to be found in his discussion of the grammar of psychological propositions that contain psychological substantives such as ‘Soul’ (MWL, 318-320). It is commonly assumed that these nouns stand for things and that the propositions that contain them abide by the ‘thing-property’ schema, where properties are

¹⁷ It may be tempting to think of this distinction in terms of direct and indirect knowledge. Wittgenstein explores this idea, albeit he ultimately rejects it: “Can it be that in my case I know directly that I have tooth-ache, in his case indirectly? As I might know directly that I have money in my pocket, indirectly that he has? No: because I couldn’t feel his tooth-ache” (MWL, 268)

predicated about things. For instance, on this view the true proposition ‘His soul is easily stirred’ (MWL, 319) predicates the property of being easily stirred about the substance denoted by ‘soul’. “Ordinary grammar doesn’t forbid us to use substantives in this way: the origin of all use of substantives & verbs is in fact a simile for physical bodies moving” (MWL, 318).

Accordingly, philosophers have provided numerous investigations that aim to unveil the substance denoted by ‘soul’. Some attempted to point to a physical object in the world, e.g., gas, breath, brain and so on, while others suggested that pointing was futile and that you must explain ‘soul’ “by some other substantive such as ‘activities’” (MWL, 320). Through these explanations philosophers construed the soul on the model of material object and designation, thereby turning it into an entity just like its physical counterparts, albeit hidden and more ethereal and abstract.

Wittgenstein contends, however, that “one great trouble our language gets us into is that we take a substantive to stand for a thing or substance” (MWL, 318). Namely, the surface grammar of language entices us to mistakenly construe psychological substantives on the model of physical substantives and, in consequence, sets us on the inauspicious path to investigate the world to find those substances denoted by psychological substantives, which are akin to physical substances albeit more abstract.

In doing so we fail to recognize that “‘concrete’ & ‘abstract’ never shed proper light” on the difference between physical phenomena and the soul “because they suggest something like ‘solid’ & ‘gaseous’ – which are comparable. We want something not comparable like ‘chair’ & ‘permission to sit in a chair’” (MWL, 318-319). The inadequacy of conceiving the soul as an abstract entity akin to its physical counterpart is further attested by the troubles that arise from philosophers’ attempts to theorize about it.

Suppose you have developed a theory: & talked about measuring distance between soul & body, there bosh would begin. Certain analogies may be irresistible, & yet only hold in a very restricted field. Read Oliver Lodge, you’ll find pseudo-experiments, & bosh – false scientific statements” (MWL, 246)

It is clear, then, that for Wittgenstein the soul is to be regarded as something substantially disanalogous to any physical entity. Accordingly, what verifies and is criterion for the existence of the soul must be quite different from what verifies and is criterion for the existence of physical entities. The description of this difference exceeds the explanatory power of and, thereby, entails accepting something more than it is allowed by existence deflationism. In other words: Despite acknowledging true psychological propositions about the soul, e.g., ‘His soul is at rest’ or ‘His soul is easily stirred’ (MWL, 319), Wittgenstein fails to concede that one can infer the existence of the soul from these propositions in the same way as they would infer the existence of physical entities from a true empirical propositions. Any such attempt entails modeling psychological and physical phenomena analogously, thus failing to recognize the differences described by Wittgenstein and which are reflected in the grammar of their respective linguistic expressions.

5.3. A new dilemma

The inadequacies that surface from the attribution of existence, fact and property deflationism to Wittgenstein make it plain that both Brandhorst and Lovibond are faced with an exegetical choice. They must either concede that Wittgenstein is no deflationist about existence, facts and properties or, alternatively, uphold their proposed interpretation by abandoning their attribution of syntacticism to Wittgenstein and arguing that there are

no such things as psychological and mathematical entities.

The reasoning underpinning this latter solution is thus: by rejecting the claim that Wittgenstein is a syntactician, Brandhorst and Lovibond can argue that declarative psychological and mathematical sentences, despite their surface grammar, are not genuine truth-apt propositions, i.e. they are not apt for truth and falsity. In consequence, there are no true psychological and mathematical propositions from which we can infer the existence of facts, properties and other entities.¹⁸ Accordingly, the non-existence of mental and mathematical entities ceases to be problematic for their proposed interpretations, allowing Brandhorst and Lovibond to salvage their exegetical claim regarding Wittgenstein's deflationist tendencies and how they provide a metaphysically unexciting way of talking about moral facts.

Notwithstanding the tensions that may surface due to Wittgenstein's acknowledgment of true mathematical (RFM, App. III, 5; LFM, 41) and psychological propositions (MWL, 319; AWL, §16), the viability of this proposed solution partly rests on Wittgenstein's description of moral discourse. Specifically, it is necessary to demonstrate that Wittgenstein treats moral sentences as truth-apt propositions, thus sanctioning the inference from undisputed true moral propositions to the existence of moral entities. Although a detailed study of this topic requires a separate investigation and the burden of proof falls on Brandhorst and Lovibond, in section 6 I examine Wittgenstein's later remarks on ethics in order to highlight some textual evidence that can dissuade us from accepting this proposed solution.

6. Wittgenstein on Ethics

Throughout this paper I have primarily focused on discussing the inadequacy of attributing existence, fact and property deflationism to Wittgenstein as a consequence of his remarks on mathematics and psychology. Little has been said, however, about Wittgenstein's remarks on ethics and the ontology of moral values. This is partly due to the fact that neither Brandhorst nor Lovibond pay much attention to them, despite their interest in Wittgenstein's later views in meta-ethics. During the remainder of this paper I want to briefly explore these remarks, as I believe they provide further evidence against Brandhorst's and Lovibond's proposed interpretations

Wittgenstein, in *Lecture on Aesthetics* and *Lectures in Cambridge* between 1930-1933 and 1932-1935, discusses the use of moral sentences that have the surface grammar of declarative sentences, e.g., 'John is good' or 'Hurting animals is bad'. Due to their resemblance to empirical propositions, it is commonly assumed that moral substantives stand for substances, adjectives for properties, declarative sentences for facts and so on (cf. see LA, Part I §1-3; MWL, 318-319, 332-333; AWL §§31-32). In other words: it encourages, rather than forbids, using moral linguistic expressions by analogy to those that are characteristic of factual/empirical discourse. Accordingly, declarative moral sentences seemingly adopt the 'thing-property' schema to relay truthful information about how the world is. 'Hurting animals is bad', for instance, appears to inform us that the action of hurting animals exemplifies the property of being bad.

However, parallel to the case of psychology discussed in 5.2, one great trouble our language gets us into in ethics is that we take a moral substantive to stand for a thing or substance, a moral adjective for a property or quality and a declarative moral sentence for a fact (see LA, Part I §1-3; MWL, 318-319, 332-333; AWL §§31-32). According to Wittgenstein, it is a mistake to construe moral expressions as denoting moral entities

¹⁸ This concession is very troublesome for Lovibond, as her interpretation rests on the claim that Wittgenstein is a syntactician (see sections 2.1 and 5).

purely due to their surface grammar. The inadequacy of this picture of moral discourse is attested, first, by the unavailability of certain ontological commitments upon which this picture relies on and, second, by the inadequate picture it portrays of the grammar of declarative moral sentences. I discuss the former issue in 6.1 and return to the latter in 6.2.

6.1. Moral values

In *Lectures in Cambridge* Wittgenstein (AWL §§31-32) briefly discusses what appears to be a realist picture of ascriptions of moral value. On this view actions or subjects are said to display instances of a certain moral property, such as goodness or badness, in the same way as they would display an empirical property, such as elasticity or greenness. This view is reliant on a ‘thing-property’ schema according to which properties and things have independently fixed identities and the application of a property to a thing is understood as a function applied to an argument. In arithmetic’s functions, such as ‘+1’ or ‘-5’, remain the same applied to different numbers that serve as arguments. Accordingly, properties remain the same applied to different things, e.g., the property of elasticity remains invariant when applied to different objects. On this standard account only the property modifies the object, not *viceversa*.

To learn whether an action has such-and-such quality it is necessary to examine its features and determine whether they are symptoms of said quality or not. For instance, “if I want to know whether a rod is elastic I can find out by looking through a microscope to see the arrangement of its particles, the nature of their arrangement being a symptom of its elasticity, or inelasticity” (AWL, §32). The viability of this investigation is dependent on whether there is some independent verification of what the property is, “otherwise the word ‘symptom’ is meaningless” (AWL, §31).¹⁹ As Wittgenstein’s puts it: “a cannot be a symptom of b unless there is a possible independent investigation of b” (AWL, §32) which allows us to examine the nature of b, i.e. the commonality that is shared by all instances of b and serves as its fixed identity. For instance, one must know what the property ‘elastic’ is in order to recognize the elasticity of an object as an indication of this property (see Kuusela Forthcoming, 3; AWL, §§31-32).

The plausibility of extending these considerations to ethics and postulating the existence of moral qualities is dependent, then, on whether there is some independent investigation of goodness that uncovers the commonality that is shared by all instances of goodness and serves as its fixed identity. Wittgenstein, unfortunately, rejects this kind of investigation in ethics (and aesthetics) on the grounds that “it is far too simple” (MWL, 332).²⁰

He explains that moral and aesthetical terms are used for a thousand different things in a thousand different ways (AWL, §32; MWL 335; LA, Part II §4). For instance, the words ‘beauty’ and ‘ugly’ when applied to a face are not the same as when applied to flowers or trees (see AWL, §32). Although we have in the latter a similar game, it is a mistake to construe these moral and aesthetical terms as having the same meaning. “Nothing would be more astonishing than if “good” [and ‘beautiful’] had the same meaning always, considering the way we learn it” (MWL, 325, my brackets).

¹⁹ Wittgenstein’s requirement for independent verification could be understood as being inconsistent with existence and property deflationism, as it imposes a condition on the existence of properties which exceeds the relatively uninformative trivial platitudes that characterize deflationism.

²⁰ Wittgenstein’s discussion of moral expressions and values runs parallel to a discussion of aesthetical ones too. This connection is not coincidental, as Wittgenstein states that practically everything is said “of ‘beautiful’ applies in a slightly different way to ‘good’” (MWL, 339; AWL, 36; cf. Kuusela Forthcoming).

If goodness and beauty can be something different in every particular case, then there is no independently fixed identity (e.g., quality or property) worthy of the name.²¹ In other words: moral and aesthetical values are not definable by reference to an entity, such as a quality, which serves as the independently fixed identity shared by all of their instantiations. Accordingly, the meaning of moral adjectives is not fixed by reference to the qualities or properties they denote. It would be astonishing that moral expressions had a general meaning covering all of its applications by referencing a certain property, object or fact (AWL, §29; cf. MWL, 325). Instead, it is only possible to ascertain their meaning by seeing how they are used in each language-game and the actions/subjects they are bound up with (for a discussion on the meaning of moral terms see Fairhurst 2019; Glock 2015).

It follows from the above that the moral evaluation of an action/subject is not to be understood as a function applied to an argument. Moral judgments “do not simply connect two things, goodness and the action independently understood, as in the case of predication” (Kuusela Forthcoming, 11). By contrast, goodness and the action are closely intertwined insofar as goodness modifies the action it is bound up with and *viceversa*. So unlike genuine properties, moral values fail to remain invariant when applied to different substances/acts. Instead, the meaning of good and beautiful is bound up with the particular acts and objects they modify (see AWL, §§31-32; MWL, 318-319, 332-335 for a detailed explanation). “Different kinds of good actions [...] may therefore not be good in the same sense” (Kuusela Forthcoming, 11).

On Wittgenstein’s picture, then, moral adjectives are better understood as having an attributive function instead of a predicative one (see Kuusela Forthcoming, 11-13 for a detailed explanation). That is, moral adjectives do not predicate certain properties about an object or a subject, but rather function as predicate modifiers that are not predicates in their own right. Thus, not only does the moral value modify the action/subject –as is in the case of the predication–, but the action/subject also modifies the moral value.

It is patent that Wittgenstein’s remarks on ascriptions of moral value do not abide by the thing-property schema that is characteristic of moral realism. On the one hand, moral values and terms are not susceptible to a fixed identity because they are said about a thousand things in a thousand ways. If goodness and badness can be something different in every particular case, then there is no quality or property worthy of the name. On the other hand, ascriptions of moral value are not understood as functions applied to arguments because moral values fail to remain invariant when applied to different substances/acts. Moral adjectives have an attributive function rather than a predicative one: they serve as predicate modifiers which are not predicates in their own right.

In consequence, Wittgenstein fails to postulate the existence of moral properties or qualities. In his own words: “there’s a great confusion in calling beauty [and goodness] a quality –an indefinable quality” (MWL, 333 my bracket). Goodness and beauty are not properties that are instantiated and exemplified by different actions/objects. It may be countered that Wittgenstein’s remarks do not exclude the possibility that goodness and beauty are complex variable qualities of some kind. But, as Kuusela (Forthcoming, 10-13) has rightly pointed out, Wittgenstein questions this too. Complex variable qualities still assume a standard account of properties according to which the property that is predicated about an object has an independently fixed identity. It is a mistaken, then, to construe moral (and aesthetical) adjectives as denoting qualities or properties. The surface grammar of these expressions is misleading and not indicative of their actual use.

²¹ This does not exclude the idea of a complex unity of good or bad in terms of family resemblance (see Kuusela 2020). However, this complex unity does not provide the fixed identity required for the postulation of moral entities.

Furthermore, the lack of a fixed identity for moral values, i.e. a commonality shared by all instances of such-and-such moral value, also jeopardizes the possibility of postulating the existence of moral objects. Wittgenstein, then, “rejects the assumption that such things as good, evil, and pains must be *things*, objects more or less like houses, albeit perhaps of a queer sort” (Richter 2018, 167). Again, it is mistaken to construe moral substantives as denoting things or substances. The surface grammar of these expressions is misleading and not indicative of their actual use (see MWL, 318-319; section 6.2).

In turn, the non-existence of moral properties and objects jeopardizes the possibility of postulating the existence of moral facts. Facts are generally understood as complex entities that are composed by objects and/or properties that stand in a certain relation. For instance, the fact ‘Wittgenstein is mortal’ is composed of Wittgenstein, which is the object, and the property of being mortal. If there are no moral properties or objects it is unclear in what sense a fact can be moral, since none of the entities that comprise the fact are moral.

Brandhorst quotes Wittgenstein’s (LA, Part I, §1-5) discussion on misleading surface grammar of moral and aesthetical adjectives, which gets us into the trouble of believing that these expressions stand for qualities or properties. He explains that Wittgenstein is not negating the existence of moral and aesthetical qualities, but rather deflating it. “That is harmless because it is empty, and it is empty because it is only a variant of ‘this is beautiful’ and ‘this is good’. It does not introduce a ‘quality’ as the objectivist conceives of it” (Brandhorst 2015, 245). On Brandhorst’s interpretation, then, Wittgenstein only takes issue with the realist’s postulation of objective moral properties (e.g. Moore’s realist view of ethical qualities) because they are thought “as a mysterious entity that has ‘shadowy’ existence in a ‘shadowy’ part of the world, and that is a mistake” (Brandhorst 2015, 245).

It is puzzling how Brandhorst infers this conclusion from the quoted remarks of Wittgenstein’s *Lecture on Aesthetics*:

The use of such a word as 'beautiful' is even more apt to be misunderstood if you look at the linguistic form of sentences in which it occurs than most other words. 'Beautiful' [and 'good'-R] is an adjective, so you are inclined to say: "This has a certain quality, that of being beautiful". (LA, Part I, §1)

If I had to say what is the main mistake made by philosophers of the present generation, including Moore, I would say that it is that when language is looked at, what is looked at is a form of words and not the use made of the form of words. (LA, Part I, §5)

In these quotations Wittgenstein is highlighting the inadequacy of inferring the existence of moral properties/qualities from meaningful moral adjectives purely due to their surface grammar. This is an instance of the widespread mistake made by philosophers who look at the form of words and not the use made of the form of words. Brandhorst’s appeal to deflationism still incurs in this same mistake. Specifically, it construes meaningful moral adjectives as denoting deflated moral qualities/properties, whose existence is inferred directly from said moral adjectives, purely due to their surface grammar. In doing so Brandhorst focuses uniquely on the form of words, not the use made of the form of words (see section 6.2 for Wittgenstein’s description of the grammar of moral adjectives, which is incompatible with Brandhorst’s proposed interpretation). The use of meaningful moral adjectives to postulate the existence of deflated moral qualities entails accepting more than Wittgenstein concedes.

Moreover, deflationism still incurs in the problems raised earlier by Wittgenstein against the idea of moral properties. Note that Wittgenstein does not take issue with the metaphysical depth or the objectivism that moral realists' attach to moral properties. Instead, his point is to bring out the inadequacy of postulating moral properties insofar as this idea is far too simple to capture the intricacies of our ascriptions of moral value. Thus, postulating deflated moral properties still entails accepting more than Wittgenstein allows insofar as they are properties that serve as the fixed identity common to all instances of a moral value. Against Brandhorst, the appeal to 'deflated' moral properties does not make this issue any less 'mysterious' and 'shadowy'.

Ensuing the rejection of moral and aesthetical qualities, Wittgenstein briefly considers the idea of moral reductionism. Moral reductionism purports to reveal the nature of moral properties and enlighten what it is for something to be good or bad. It holds that moral facts, properties and objects are identical to the non-moral facts, properties and objects they are reduced to and which can be expressed using non-moral vocabulary.

Wittgenstein (AWL, §34-36) discusses reductionism and its implications by examining the widespread temptation of reducing ethics to psychology. On this view, moral values are reduced to mental states (e.g., pleasure or pain), which serve as their corresponding non-moral properties. This is accomplished by specifying the *causal connections* that warrant the reductive identity claim between certain values and these non-moral properties. These *causal connections* are expressed by psychological and sociological propositions, such as 'x is good or beautiful if x gives us pleasure', which are hypothesis that can be confirmed or disconfirmed through empirical investigation. The question about the goodness of an action, then, is to be answered by psychological and sociological propositions which cite *causes*.

Wittgenstein counters that the causal reductive explanation of moral values that is characteristic of moral reductionism does not remove the ethical puzzle one feels when asked what makes an action good (AWL, §34) –at times Wittgenstein's remarks are reminiscent of Moore's Open-Question Argument. The question about the goodness of an action does not demand specifying the physical effects caused by the action on the human body and how they are causally connected with the evaluation. Ethical puzzles do not demand causes, but rather *reasons*. "The difference between a reason and a cause is brought out as follows: the investigation of a reason entails as an essential part one's agreement with it, whereas the investigation of a cause is carried out experimentally" (AWL, §36). Ethics, insofar as it demands *reasons*, is no science nor should it be reduced to science.²²

Thus, reducing moral values to non-moral properties does not yield an adequate explanation of moral ascriptions of value that enlightens to us as what it is for an act or object to be good or beautiful –as Brandhorst (2015, 248) himself recognizes. Furthermore, reductionism is still predicated around the problematic idea that moral values have a fixed identity. Wittgenstein's criticism of moral properties and objects is not predicated on their mystifying nature, but rather on the simplicity of this explanation (see MWL, 332).

In conclusion, Wittgenstein's remarks on ascriptions of moral value and moral reductionism indicate a dismissive attitude towards the postulation of the existence of

²² Wittgenstein also discusses the inadequacy of reducing ethics to sociology and psychology in his conversations with Rhees. He explains that if we simply describe "the Sitten und Gebräuche of various tribes, this would not be ethics" (Wittgenstein, Rhees & Citron 2015, 27). Note that, by contrast, on Brandhorst's (2015, 245-246) interpretation moral customs, rules, behaviors and prescriptions are parts of human life that constitute the reality that corresponds to ethics.

moral entities. In neither case does Wittgenstein take issue with metaphysical depth associated to these entities by moral realists and reductionists, but rather highlights the inadequacy of postulating these entities altogether. Thus, even if Lovibond and Brandhorst are able to overcome the problems discussed in sections 4 and 5, there seems to be insufficient textual evidence to uphold the claim that Wittgenstein provides a novel way of postulating the existence of moral facts. In other words: The (dubious) appeal to deflationism does not afford or deliver ontological conclusions desired by Lovibond and Brandhorst. It is for this reason that Wittgenstein scholars, such as Kuusela (Forthcoming), have recently argued that Wittgenstein's moral realism forgoes the postulation of moral properties or naturalistic reduction.²³

6.2. Moral discourse

As I have suggested at various points of 6.1, the inadequacy of inferring the existence of moral entities from moral sentences, adjectives and substantives is further attested by Wittgenstein's description of the grammar of these expressions. According to Wittgenstein, it is commonly assumed that moral substantives denote substances, moral adjectives denote properties and declarative moral sentences denote facts due to their surface form (cf. see LA, Part I §1-3; MWL, 318-319, 332-333; AWL §§31-32). However, the surface form of moral language plays us tricks, leading to confusions about its grammar. Specifically, there is great confusion in describing moral expressions as denoting moral entities. In order to get clear about the grammar of moral linguistic expressions, which often lacks openness to view (cf. MWL, 318-319, 332-333; LA Part I, §3), Wittgenstein suggests that one must examine the use, rather than the form, of these linguistic expressions.

In order to adequately describe the grammar of moral linguistic expressions Wittgenstein examines how they are taught, as it destroys many of misconceptions about their grammar and provides primitive language-games in which they are used (LA Part I, §5). He explains that they are learned roughly as interjections that substitute facial expressions or other gestures of approval or disapproval (LA, Part I §§5-7). Take for instance, the word 'good'. "We do not as children discover the quality of" goodness in such-and-such action "and find that these are qualities" such-and-such action "has in common with it" (AWL, §32).²⁴ Instead, 'good' is taught to substitute a certain *gesture* that expresses a feeling of approval about something, such as food, music or actions (LA, Part I §5).

Accordingly, declarative moral sentences and moral judgments are primarily used to replace certain *gestures* that express natural reactions of approval or disapproval about something (LA, Part I §5-7, §10; Wittgenstein, Rhees & Citron 2015, 30; see also Glock 2015, 121-123; Fairhurst 2019, 6). Their meaning is given by the natural reactions of

²³ The inadequacy of this exegetical claim may be further attested by Wittgenstein's dismiss of evidence or proof. Wittgenstein explains that in ethical discussions there is argument and reasons for/against, but "there isn't generally proof" which serves as evidence that conclusively settles a discussion (Wittgenstein, Rhees & Citron 2015, 28; cf. LA, Part III §2; MWL, 331). The non-existence of proof or evidence is a serious challenge to Brandhorst's proposed interpretation, especially taking into account that he concedes that it is possible to speak of ethical objectivity, albeit in a deflationary sense. It seems incongruent to affirm the existence of (deflated) moral facts, truths and objectivity and, simultaneously, rejecting the idea that there is proof or evidence in ethics. On Brandhorst's interpretation Wittgenstein should allow for evidence ethics, albeit it may be different to that of physics. However, there is no such admission in Wittgenstein's writings on ethics.

²⁴ In this quotation Wittgenstein originally discusses the grammar of 'beautiful'. Nevertheless, these considerations can be extended to 'good' insofar as practically everything that is said "of 'beautiful' applies in a slightly different way to 'good'" (MWL, 339; AWL, 36).

approval or disapproval they express by replacing these gestures.²⁵ For instance, ‘This is a noble action’ is a verbal expression that replaces, and simply says, ‘ah’ together with a facial expression of approval (see Wittgenstein, Rhees & Citron 2015, 30; LA, Part I §7). An ethical sentence, then, “is a personal act. Not a *statement of fact*. (Like an exclamation of admiration)” (PPO, 85 my emphasis; cf. MWL, 318-333; AWL, §31-32). Contrary to what their surface form indicates, these expressions do not serve the purpose of relaying truthful information about the world or denoting moral facts.

Wittgenstein’s description of the grammar of declarative moral sentences and moral judgments is also extended to the moral substantives and adjectives that comprise them. With regards to the former he notes one great trouble our language gets us into is that we mistakenly take moral substantives “to stand for a thing or substance. Ordinary grammar doesn’t forbid us to use substantives in this way: the origin of all use of substantives & verbs is in fact a simile for physical bodies moving” (MWL, 318-319). But ultimately it is a mistake to construe moral substantives as denoting (non-existing) moral objects or substances. Their surface form is not indicative of their use in language.

With regards to the latter, as explained above, moral adjectives are learned roughly as interjections that substitute *gestures* that express feelings of approval and disapproval (LA, Part I §5-8). There is a great confusion, then, in saying that moral adjectives denote or stand for qualities/properties in virtue of their surface form (LA Part I §1-3; AWL §§31-32). “Problems about what these words are about, what their real subject is, [which is called ‘beautiful’ or ‘good’.-R.] don’t come up at all” (LA, Part I §8). Wittgenstein forgoes the need to postulate the existence of moral properties for these linguistic expressions to be meaningful. Furthermore, he explains that moral adjectives, such as a ‘good’, ‘bad’ or ‘just’, hardly play any role at all in moral discourse (LA, Part I §8).

Thus, summarizing, one of the great troubles language gets us into is taking moral names as standing for objects, moral adjectives for properties and declarative moral sentences for facts due to their surface form (see LA, Part I §1-3; MWL, 318-319, 332-333; AWL §§31-32). By examining the use, rather than the form, of moral linguistic expressions one can get clear about their grammar, which often lacks openness to view. Specifically, according to Wittgenstein, one can appreciate that these expressions are primarily used to express natural reactions of approval or disapproval, not relaying truthful information about the world or denoting moral entities. Wittgenstein, therefore, foregoes the need to postulate moral entities for moral discourse to be meaningful and useful (see also Kuusela Forthcoming).

Note that, by contrast, Brandhorst’s proposed interpretation is predicated around the premise that Wittgenstein needs to postulate the existence of moral entities for moral discourse to be meaningful and useful (these considerations may also extend to Lovibond’s interpretation, albeit it is less clear). At various points of his work Brandhorst explains that correspondence to reality is a necessary requirement moral language must fulfill in order to avoid being “a game played merely for entertainment” or “some empty formalism without use” (Brandhorst 2015, 244). In other words: moral language has a use insofar as it corresponds to, and is interwoven into, the tapestry of our life:

We ask or demand or wish for certain things of one another; we praise people for what they do or achieve; we promise to do certain things and accept obligations

²⁵ Wittgenstein seemingly advocates for moral expressivism and emotivism. Expressivist and emotivist, like Wittgenstein, claim that moral terms, analogously to interjections such as ‘boo’ or ‘ah’, are primarily used to express attitudes of approval and disapproval and other non-cognitive mental states (see Glock 2015 & Fairhurst 2019 for a detailed defense of this connection).

to others; we criticise and we reproach; we lay down and discuss rules for our conduct; we ask ourselves what we should do; we build and revise a conception of how we should live, of what is worth caring about, and of what makes our lives worth living. All this – and much more could be added – is real. It marks the way we live. It is important to us, shaping our relations to ourselves as well as to others. In this way, it provides the framework for our use of ethical language. So as before, it would be misleading to say that no reality corresponds to that language. (Brandhorst 2015, 244)

It is this reality, the reality of human affairs, to which ethics corresponds (Brandhorst 2015, 246).

Unfortunately, there are certain inconsistencies in Brandhorst's reading of Wittgenstein's later moral philosophy. First, Brandhorst is suggesting that moral language corresponds to the customs, traditions, rules, behaviors and prescriptions which make up the reality of human affairs. It is in virtue of this correspondence to reality that moral language has a *meaningful* use. It is questionable, however, whether the descriptions of these customs, traditions, rules, behaviors and prescriptions can be regarded genuine moral sentences. In his conversations with Rush Rhees Wittgenstein explains: "Supposing you simply describe the Sitten und Gebräuche of various tribes, this would not be ethics" (Wittgenstein, Rhees & Citron 2015, 27). Thus, Brandhorst must clarify in what sense moral language corresponds to reality, as the description of customs and traditions is not ethics. Moreover, Brandhorst must explain in what sense the examples he provides are to be regarded as ethical facts (see section 6.1).

Second, Brandhorst rightly points out that the reality of human affairs provides the framework for our use of moral language. This idea is implicit in Wittgenstein's notion of 'language-game', which brings into prominence the fact that the speaking of language is part of an activity, or of a form of life" (PI, §23). That is, language-games are social linguistic activities that are embedded within the affairs and practices of a form of life. All linguistic practices must be understood against the background of these non-linguistic affairs and practices. The same applies to moral language: to get clear about the meaning of moral terms one must pay attention to the non-linguistic activities it is interwoven with (see e.g. LA, Part I §35; MWL, 321-322).

The problem, however, arises when Brandhorst concludes from the above that moral language corresponds to this reality that serves as the context for moral linguistic practices. This inference is made by Brandhorst in the transition between the two final sentences of the quote supplied above and is *without foundation*. Saying that the reality of human affairs is the framework for our use of moral language tells us *nothing* about the use of moral language. It *only* provides the context within which moral language-games take place. Thus, correspondence to reality is an independent idea that requires further explanation, especially taking into account that they are inconsistent with the textual evidence presented above.

The inadequacy of Brandhorst's inference can be further attested by Wittgenstein's remarks on avowals. Avowals are also to be understood in connection to the non-linguistic affairs and practices of a form of life within which they are embedded. We cry; we smile; we learn to express our feelings; we learn to recognize how others feel in virtue of their behavior; we learn to behave in such-and-such way when others have such-and-such feeling; for instance we attend to others when we think they are in pain. All of this is real. It marks the way we live, shaping our relations to ourselves as well as to others. In this way, it provides the framework for our use of avowals. However, it is a mistake to infer that avowals correspond to this reality. Avowals describe first-person

psychological sentences that are used to express mental states. “Negatively, this indicates that they are not descriptions or reports of private mental entities encountered in an inner realm” (Glock 1996, 50). That is, avowals are not in the business of referencing or corresponding to reality.

Finally, Brandhorst’s work rests on the false premise that correspondence to reality is a necessary requirement moral language must fulfill in order to avoid being “a game played merely for entertainment” or “some empty formalism without use” (Brandhorst 2015, 244). Reconsider the case of avowals: despite their lack of correspondence to reality, they play a crucial role in human life. They allow human beings express their feelings, beliefs, attitudes and other mental states to others. For instance, verbal expressions of pain are crucial for warning others about our need to visit the doctors immediately due to an illness.

Foregoing correspondence to reality does entrain that avowals are games played for entertainment or empty formalisms without use. Their expressive function alone suffices for them to realize their crucial role in human life. It is important, therefore to “make a radical break with the idea that language always functions in one way, always serves the same purpose: to convey thoughts—which may be about houses, pains, good and evil, or anything else you please” (PI: §304). Correspondence to reality is a not a prerequisite for language to be useful or meaningful.

Analogously, moral judgments need not correspond to reality for them to be interwoven with, and play a crucial role in, human life. Wittgenstein’s description of the grammar of moral discourse emphasizes its expressive function, while showing that there is great confusion in assuming that it is used to relay truthful information about the world or denote moral entities. However, foregoing the need to postulate moral entities to which moral expressions correspond does not entrain reducing moral language to “a game played merely for entertainment” or “some empty formalism without use” (Brandhorst 2015, 244). (It seems unlikely that moral non-descriptivists and anti-realists take moral discourse to be an empty formalism played for entertainment as a consequence of their rejection of a moral reality to which moral discourse corresponds).

Furthermore, moral judgments can be *about* the world without denoting mysterious moral entities, such as objects, properties or facts. Christensen (2011) argues that, according to Wittgenstein, moral judgments are not a borderline case of pure normative and non-descriptive sentences. Instead, they involve relevant descriptions about the features of the actions that make us judge them such-and-so. For instance, understanding ‘Hurting animals is cruel’ involves relevant descriptions about the features of the action of hurting animals. However, this does not entail that moral judgments predicate moral properties/qualities about an action or denote *moral* facts. Instead, they express attitudes of approval and disapproval towards some way the world is.

Conclusion

In this paper I have argued that Wittgenstein does not provide a novel conception of moral facts, properties and objects by adopting deflationism. First, I outlined some inconsistencies in Brandhorst’s characterization of fact deflationism as a *local* position. Second, I argued that, while these inconsistencies are solved by Lovibond’s interpretation, the proposed solution fails to capture the intricacies of Wittgenstein’s later work. The attribution of deflationism does not do justice to Wittgenstein’s later work and, thereby, that the appeal to deflationism does not afford or substantiate the exegetical claims made by Lovibond and Brandhorst. Thirdly, I examined Wittgenstein’s remarks on moral values and grammar of moral discourse, largely ignored by Brandhorst and

Lovibond, in order to make plain that there is insufficient textual evidence to uphold their exegetical claims.

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